

MODELLING SLIT TAPE DEPOSITION DURING AUTOMATED FIBRE PLACEMENT

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1. Introduction

With the increasing demand for composites and economic pressure for preserving competitiveness in today's global market, it is no longer possible to rely on hand lay-up techniques in composite manufacturing [1]. Automation is a necessary step since it improves reliability, consistency and reduces material wastage [2-4].

Fig. 1: Twin-headed AFP machine in action at the UK's National Composites Centre [5]

Automated Fibre Placement (AFP) is one of the main technologies suitable for manufacturing simple to complex laminated composite structures including doubly-curved regions [6-8]. It consists in laying down, onto the surface of a mould or substrate, multiple layers of narrow tapes simultaneously during each sequence (also referred to as course). These slit tapes are fed through a fibre delivery

system into a poly-articulated fibre-placement head where they are collimated, see Fig. 1. The number of collimated tapes depends on the width requirements and on the complexity of the part geometry to be manufactured.

For example, one of the AFP machines available at the UK's National Composites Centre (NCC) in Fig. 1 can deliver up to 8 slit tapes (6.35 mm wide each) per head in the same sequence. This number can be reduced depending on the local complexity of the part geometry. Each tape is dispersed at its own speed up to 0.8 m/s, allowing the creation of fibre-steered laminates. It can be cut on-the-fly then restarted independently from the others. Tape placement accuracy ranges from 0.1 to 0.5 mm [9].

Fig. 2: Schematic illustration of the NCC AFP head

To consolidate the prepreg, remove surface irregularities and reduce the amount of entrapped air between the deposited plies, an elastomeric compaction roller is used, see Fig. 2. Uniform compaction is essential for producing high quality parts. On some AFP machines, adaptive rollers have been proposed [10,11], the goal being to further minimise vacuum debulking operations which

detrimentally affect productivity. AFP machines can apply a load in a range of 10–400 lb (45–1,800 N) during the process [12].

In practice, a heat source is used ahead of the compaction roller to enhance material tack and formability before compressing the tapes, see Fig. 2. This is crucial for preventing material separation from the mould or substrate and avoiding defect formation. Laser heaters [13], infrared heaters [14] and hot gas torches [15] are the most common heating tools currently used on AFP machine heads. Campbell has reported that modern tape-laying heads use a hot-air heating system for pre-heating the tape at a temperature ranging from 80 to 110°F (25–45°C) [12]. Obviously, the ideal layup temperature depends upon the prepreg material used [16,17]. For a typical highly toughened carbon fibre-reinforced epoxy prepreg, Calawa and Nancarrow have reported that 35°C is the ideal layup temperature [18].

Today, automated ply deposition strategies are defined empirically. This process is labour-intensive and therefore expensive. Extensive research is underway at the NCC to further improve productivity while offsetting initial capital expenditure in AFP equipment, the goal being to open up AFP to new market opportunities and applications in aerospace, automotive, renewable energy and consumer goods. To better understand the behaviour of the slit tapes during AFP and therefore anticipate on layup possibilities whilst optimising paths, it is necessary to have recourse to numerical simulations such as finite element (FE) analyses.

Recently, Lukaszewicz and Potter [19] have proposed an approach for modelling isothermal compaction of a thermoset prepreg during automated tape laying (ATL). The material was modelled as an homogeneous elasto-plastic material. Viscous effects were neglected because of the short compactions times (below 0.1 s) to which the uncured prepreg is typically subjected.

In this paper, the heat source ahead of the compaction roller in Fig. 2 is ignored and the AFP process is assumed isothermal throughout with a prepreg at 20, 30 or 40°C. The different block of materials involved, i.e. the compaction roller and the uncured prepreg material, are experimentally characterised prior to simulating. Preliminary 2D FE analyses are then proposed to simulate the process.

To account for lateral contact between adjacent tapes, 3D analyses are subsequently performed. It is demonstrated that 2D models can provide reasonable results but only under restrictive conditions. With the 3D model, it is revealed that slit tapes exhibit lateral elastic ‘bumps’ at the actual position of the roller that prevent tape/tape gaps from closing.

2. Material characterisation

2.1. Compression roller

The compaction roller under consideration in this study is cylindrical (outer diameter: 70 mm, width: 60 mm, bearing diameter: 30 mm). Made from polyurethane (PU) foam, the core is protected on its outer surface by a layer 0.5 mm thick made of perfluoroalkoxy (PFA), see Fig. 3a. The latter is aimed at reducing friction when the roller interacts with any surface.

Fig. 3: (a) Roller testing configuration and (b) corresponding FE model

Since the properties of each block of material were unknown, an engineering material characterisation was undertaken. It consisted in homogenising the whole roller (PU and PFA) as an effective linear elastic isotropic material. To get the required properties, i.e. E_e and ν_e , the roller was loaded in compression between two rigid plates using a 10 kN displacement-controlled servo-electric universal test frame machine. The experimental load-displacement curve was then plotted and compared to that produced from simulating using the 2D FE model in Fig. 3b produced in Abaqus/Standard (version 6.11). For symmetry reasons, only a quarter-geometry was modelled and, therefore, symmetry boundary

conditions were used where appropriate. The deformable part of the roller was meshed with 360 4-noded fully integrated elements of type CPE4 having a plane strain formulation. A quarter of the metallic bearing was modelled using 15 2-noded rigid elements of type R2D2 as an inner circular surface. The latter was connected to the surrounding flexible part of the roller using tie constraints. One 2-noded rigid element of type R2D2 was used to model the upper rigid surface of the test machine in contact with the upper surface of the roller. Contact interactions were modelled using a penalty contact algorithm defined with a zero Coulomb friction coefficient.

Fig. 4: Load-displacement response of the roller under through-thickness compression.

After iterating on the effective properties, $E_e = 3$ MPa and $\nu_e = 0.1$ were found to be the most suitable pair for fitting the experimental curve as shown in Fig. 4. It is important to mention that friction at the roller/rigid plate interface was assessed by increasing progressively the Coulomb friction coefficient up to 0.2. No significant effect was found on the FE curve in Fig. 4 and, consequently, frictionless contact conditions were assumed in all the subsequent simulations.

2.2. Uncured carbon/epoxy prepreg

According to Lukaszewicz and Potter [19], uncured carbon/epoxy prepreps can be modelled as orthotropic elasto-plastic materials when through-thickness compaction times are short (below 0.1 s). To model the elastic regime of deformation, it is necessary to determine the 6 usual engineering constants: the Young's moduli, E_1 , E_2 and E_3 ,

Poisson's ratio's, ν_{12} , ν_{13} and ν_{23} , and shear moduli, G_{12} , G_{13} and G_{23} . Since slit tapes can be assumed as transversely isotropic: $E_2 = E_3$, $\nu_{12} = \nu_{13}$, $G_{12} = G_{13}$, and $G_{23} = E_2/2(1 + \nu_{23})$. For temperatures below 60°C, typical prepreps remain in a rubbery state [20]. They can therefore be considered as incompressible materials [21]. This leads to having $\nu_{12} = 0.5$ and $\nu_{23} = 1 - E_2/2E_1 \simeq 1$ and, therefore, the engineering constants to be determined experimentally are only E_1 , E_3 and G_{12} .

To model anisotropic yielding, Hill's criterion is used:

$$F(\sigma_{22} - \sigma_{33})^2 + G(\sigma_{33} - \sigma_{11})^2 + H(\sigma_{11} - \sigma_{22})^2 + 2L\sigma_{23}^2 + 2M\sigma_{31}^2 + 2N\sigma_{12}^2 = 1 \quad (1)$$

It requires only 6 anisotropic parameters, namely F , G , H , L , M and N , which are defined according to the anisotropic yield stress ratios R_{ij} as:

$$\begin{aligned} F &= \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{1}{R_{22}^2} + \frac{1}{R_{33}^2} - \frac{1}{R_{11}^2} \right) & L &= \frac{3}{2R_{23}^2} \\ G &= \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{1}{R_{33}^2} + \frac{1}{R_{11}^2} - \frac{1}{R_{22}^2} \right) & M &= \frac{3}{2R_{13}^2} \\ H &= \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{1}{R_{11}^2} + \frac{1}{R_{22}^2} - \frac{1}{R_{33}^2} \right) & N &= \frac{3}{2R_{12}^2} \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where $R_{ii} = \sigma_{ii}^y / \sigma_0^y$ and $R_{ij} = \tau_{ij}^y \sqrt{3} / \sigma_0^y$ ($i, j = 1, 2, 3$ and $i \neq j$). σ_{ii}^y and τ_{ij}^y are the measured tensile and shear yield strength values when σ_{ii} and τ_{ij} are applied respectively. σ_0^y is the user-defined reference yield stress specified for the plasticity definition. In the present case, $\sigma_0^y = \sigma_{33}^y$ and therefore $R_{33} = \sigma_{33}^y / \sigma_0^y = 1$.

As shown later in Fig. 6, unidirectional prepreps under through-thickness compaction exhibit strengthening. To capture this behaviour, Ludwik's phenomenological equation can be used [19]:

$$\sigma = A \epsilon_p^m + \sigma_y \quad (3)$$

where σ is the true stress at some plastic strain ϵ_p , σ_y is the initial material yield stress, and A and m are material-dependent coefficients.

The following sub-sections present the experimental tests reported in [22] for determining the required material properties: E_1 , E_3 and G_{12} . Details of these tests along with the corresponding results are recalled below for completeness.

2.2.1. In-plane tensile tests (E_1)

Several slit tapes were laterally collimated then cut to give a sample 520 mm long and 75 mm wide. Composite endtabs 60 mm long were bonded to the ends using localised heating for 20 min at 180°C, giving a gauge length of 400 mm. The endtabs were then wrapped with emery cloth to increase friction and avoid slippage when mounted in mechanical grips. A 27 kN servo-hydraulic machine was used to test the samples in pure tension at a controlled load rate of 100 N/s. Strain was recorded using digital image correlation on a spray paint speckle pattern applied onto the gauge region. After calibrating, 5 samples were tested up to failure at room temperature. In the end, an average tensile Young's modulus, $E_1 = 83$ MPa (CV = 10.6 %) and an average tensile strength, $\sigma_{11}^y = 648$ MPa (CV = 9.9 %) were obtained.

2.2.2. Off-axis tensile test (G_{12})

According to Potter [23], uncured prepregs deform as if they were in pure shear loading when the fibre direction is at 15° from the tensile testing direction. Therefore, similar samples to those introduced in sub-section 2.2.1 were manufactured but with this off-axis fibre direction. Their dimensions were however different to accommodate different grips 60 mm long. Samples 50 mm wide and 420 mm long were prepared with a 300 mm gauge length onto which a spray paint speckle pattern was also applied. Controlled displacements at 1 mm/min were used to test 5 samples up to failure at room temperature. This gave an average shear modulus, $G_{12} = 156$ MPa (CV = 9.4 %) and an average shear strength, $\tau_{12}^y = 6.3$ MPa (CV = 3.3 %).

2.2.3. Through-thickness compressive tests (E_3)

For small strains, the prepreg's through-thickness response is dominated by the resin's properties whose response is temperature, time and load dependent. In this exercise, samples 100 mm long, 60 mm wide and 8 plies thick (2.264 mm) were prepared. A micrometer was used to determine the samples' thicknesses whilst length and width were measured using a caliper. It is important to note that the samples were pressed under vacuum at room temperature for 1 hour prior to testing. The test setup was made of two heated flat plates in contact with the sample via layers of release film to help eliminate friction, see Fig. 5. The latter enabled free in-plane expansion of the prepreg.

Fig. 5: Experimental test setup

Fig. 6: Stress-strain curve fitting using Ludwik's equation during plastic deformation of the uncured prepreg at various temperatures [19,22].

With an accuracy of $\pm 1^\circ\text{C}$, 8 samples were tested at 20, 30 or 40°C each. Load control at 10 kN/min was applied up to 15 kN. By using the relative thickness change of the sample with respect to its initial thickness, engineering strains were calculated for each sample after unloading the samples. This was replicated after 12 hours to verify that no further relaxation had occurred. It is important to note that the applied compressive stress was calculated by using the final samples' dimensions. Through-thickness modulus, E_3 , was calculated by dividing the applied stress and the engineering through-thickness strain. In the end, the average E_3 value at 20, 30 and 40°C were found to be 50.05, 28.86 MPa and 11.86 MPa respectively. From data fitting in Fig. 6, the yield strength values were estimated to be: 0.06 MPa at 20°C, and 0.006 MPa at 30 and 40°C. It is important to note that all these material property values were measured from samples 8-ply and not 1-ply thick. Therefore, although these values

may be different for single ply samples, they were used as such in this study.

2.2.4. Summary of the experimental results

Table 1 recapitulates all the prepreg's elastic properties identified from material characterisation. Results at room temperature were assumed to be at 20°C. Constant longitudinal Young's modulus, E_1 , and in-plane shear modulus, G_{12} , were assumed regardless of the temperature. These properties were not expected to significantly affect the results. Table 2 summarises the plastic properties identified from data fitting in Fig. 6.

Temp.	E_l [MPa]	E_t [MPa]	ν_{lt} [-]	ν_{tt} [-]	G_{lt} [MPa]	G_{tt} [MPa]
20°C	83,000	50.05	0.5	~1	156	12.51
30°C	83,000	28.86	0.5	~1	156	7.21
40°C	83,000	11.86	0.5	~1	156	2.84

Table 1: Uncured prepreg elastic properties at various temperatures. Subscripts 'l' and 't' denote longitudinal and transverse directions respectively.

Temp.	K [MPa]	m [-]	σ_0 [MPa]
20°C	800	1.56	0.06
30°C	490	1.59	0.006
40°C	202	1.5	0.006

Table 2: Uncured prepreg plastic properties at various temperatures.

R_{11}	R_{22}	R_{33}	R_{12}	R_{13}	R_{23}
10,800	1	1	182	182	1

Table 3: Anisotropic yield stress ratios defining the anisotropic parameters in Eq. (3).

From testing at room temperature, the longitudinal tensile and in-plane shear yield strengths were found to be $\sigma_{11}^y = 648$ MPa and $\tau_{12}^y = 6.3$ MPa respectively. By assuming the reference through-thickness yield strength to be $\sigma_{33}^y = 0.06$ MPa, this leads to having $R_{11} = 10,800$ and $R_{12} = 182$. Since the prepreg is transversely isotropic within the 2-3-plane, $R_{22} = R_{33} = 1$ and $R_{13} = R_{12} = 182$. In the case of pure shear stress within the same plane, the von Mises criterion gives $\tau_{23}^y = \sigma_0^y / \sqrt{3}$ and therefore $R_{23} = 1$. Table 3 summarises the yield stress ratios to be used in all the FE analyses. They

are assumed to remain constant regardless of the prepreg temperature.

3. Material model validation

To validate the proposed elasto-plastic material model, prepreg compression tests were performed at 20, 30 or 40°C using a 6 kN compressive load. They were then modelled in Abaqus/Standard (version 6.11). Owing to material symmetry, one eighth of the sample in Fig. 5 was meshed using a single 8-noded hexahedral element of type C3D8, see Fig. 7. Symmetry boundary conditions were used where appropriate, i.e. on planes ABCD, ABFE and ADHE. Homogeneous orthotropic properties given in Tables 1 to 3 were inputted. A single 4-noded rigid element of type R3D4 was used to model the upper plate since its stiffness is much higher than that of the prepreg. The plate was fully constrained but free to move vertically along the z-axis. A vertical concentrated load of 1.5 kN was then applied to the rigid upper plate via a reference node. Frictionless contact between the top surface EFGH of the prepreg and the rigid plate was assumed to account for the presence of the release film introduced to help eliminate friction in Fig. 5.

Fig. 7: Overview of the compression test FE model (1/8 sample) for the material model validation

Table 4 compares experimental and FE results in terms of through-thickness engineering strains, e_{zz} . Each FE strain is within 10 % of the corresponding experimental value which is acceptable given usual scatter observed in experimental results.

Temp.	20°C	30°C	40°C
Experimental	-14.13	-18.11	-25.27
FE result	-12.73	-19.36	-26.59
Difference	-9.9 %	6.9 %	5.2 %

Table 4: Comparison between experimental and FE through-thickness engineering strain e_{zz} [in $\mu\text{m}/\text{m}$].

4. Finite element modelling

The AFP process to be modelled was limited to one layer of prepreg laid down onto a flat panel. During each course, 8 slit tapes $w_t = 6.35$ mm nominally wide and $t_t = 0.283$ mm nominally thick [19,22] were simultaneously laid down, see Fig. 8. The elastomeric roller characterised in Fig. 3 was used to apply a compaction load ranging from 100 to 600 N.

The process was assumed isothermal throughout at 20, 30 or 40°C. This enabled the heat source and the incoming prepreg tape angle ahead of the compaction roller to be neglected in all the analyses. The modelled tape length was restricted to 100 mm to decrease the computation times and because all the material models are strain rate independent. Abaqus/Standard (version 6.11) was used for performing all the simulations.

Fig. 8: AFP configuration with 8 slit tapes to be compacted by the compliant roller

4.1. Preliminary 2D FE modelling

2D FE analyses were first undertaken using the mesh in Fig. 9. Plane stress and plane strain conditions were used for the tape and the roller respectively. This is appropriate since the slit tape is only 6.35 mm wide and the roller is nearly 10 times wider than the latter. Obviously, tape/tape gap widths were assumed to be such that no lateral tape interaction occurs in this approach.

The slit tape was modelled using a single layer of 500 4-noded fully integrated elements of type CPS4. To prevent rigid body motion, the 2 left-end nodes were constrained horizontally whilst all the bottom

nodes were constrained vertically to simulate the presence of the rigid flat panel.

The whole roller was homogenised as a single equivalent isotropic material, see section 2.1. It was meshed with 2,880 4-noded fully integrated elements of type CPE4. It is important to note that the outer surface was refined with a similar element size to that of the slit tape to get smooth contact interactions.

The metallic bearing was modelled using 120 2-noded rigid elements of type R2D2 as an inner circular surface. The latter was connected to the surrounding flexible part of the roller using tie constraints. It was controlled using a central reference node. To model interactions at the tape/roller interface, a surface-to-surface penalty contact algorithm with a zero friction coefficient was chosen. It is important to note that the roller was positioned 20 mm away from the left-end of the tape to avoid edge effects when the roller in Fig. 9 is significantly deformed.

Fig. 9: Overview of the 2D FE model

The calculations were broken down into two distinct steps. The first modelled the compaction phase of the tapes when a load ranging from 1.96 to 11.81 N per millimetre width was applied in the y-direction at the reference node of the bearing. This is consistent with applying loads ranging from 100 to 600 N onto 8 slit tapes 6.35 mm wide each.

During the first step, symmetry boundary conditions were prescribed along the roller's vertical plane of symmetry to reduce the number of unknowns in the non-linear system of equations to be solved. The latter were then released at the beginning of the second step modelling the roller compacting the prepreg. For this second step, a dynamic implicit formulation was chosen. The roller was subjected to a constant acceleration of 0.5 m/s^2 during 0.5 s. This

made it move over a distance of 62.5 mm, and therefore remain on the prepreg during the whole simulation. It is important to mention that the applied roller speed is not expected to have a significant effect on the FE results because the material models used are all strain rate independent.

Fig. 10: Predicted tape thickness distributions from the 2D model for various compaction loads and at a constant 40°C layup temperature (initial tape thickness: $t_t = 0.283$ mm).

From the nodal coordinates at the upper surface of the tape, $t_t = 0.283$ mm initially thick, it was possible to plot its thickness distribution at 40°C for example, see Fig. 10. To properly interpret the graph, it is necessary to recall that the roller starts in $x = 20$ mm at the beginning of the simulation and ends in $x = 82.5$ mm when the simulation stops. The curves show significant through-thickness deformations at the actual position of the roller, up to 7.3 % when $F_c = 600$ N. This is due to high longitudinal tape stiffness in the x-direction. Therefore deformation is mainly accumulated through the thickness since no lateral (out-of-plane) effects are accounted for.

Fig. 11: Cross-section view of 2 adjacent slit tapes laid down simultaneously.

When post-processing the FE results, it was found that the prepreg was subjected to elastic plus plastic

deformations just below the roller. When the latter moved away, the prepreg lost its elastic deformation while only plastic deformations remained giving the form of the curve shown in Fig. 10. The plastic deformations appeared relatively limited because of the exponential strain hardening nature of the prepreg modelled with a hardening coefficient m greater than 1 in Eq. (3).

To be able to determine the resulting gap width, w'_g , between adjacent slit tapes from the 2D FE results, it is necessary to rationalise using the material incompressibility assumption throughout the process. Therefore, by assuming the tapes having their vertical plane of symmetry remaining at the same position during ply deposition, they can spread equally in both lateral directions (along the z-axis in Fig. 11). By idealising the slit tapes' cross sections as rectangle [24], the resulting gap width after compaction is therefore given as:

$$w'_g = w_g + w_t \left(1 - \frac{t_t}{t'_t}\right) \quad (4)$$

where w_g , w_t and t_t are respectively the initial gap width, the initial tape width and the final slit tape thickness, and t'_t is the final slit tape thickness after compaction. By assuming w_g to be wide enough to avoid lateral tape/tape interactions, e.g. $w_g = 0.5$ mm, it is possible to plot the graph in Fig. 12. Significant material lateral spreading is predicted in the region deformed elasto-plastically causing two noticeable elastic 'bumps' in $x = 82.5$ mm. This is directly due to the levels of thickness reduction shown in Fig. 10.

Fig. 12: Predicted tape/tape gap width distributions at 40°C from the 2D FE model as a function of the compaction load F_c ($w_t = 0.5$ mm).

By measuring t'_t in $x = 50$ mm on the graph in Fig. 12 for each load case, and by replicating the same procedure on similar results at 20 and 30°C, it is

possible to plot the graph in Fig. 13. It can be noticed that the final gap width is a decreasing non-linear function of the compaction load regardless of the layup temperature. In addition, the graph shows that the higher the layup temperature is, the more compacted the prepreg is since it is more compliant.

Fig. 13: Predicted tape/tape gap width after compaction as a function of the compaction load for various temperatures.

4.2. 3D FE modelling

In the previous FE results, physical phenomena occurring across the width (z-direction) such as lateral plastic flow and tape/tape interactions were ignored. It is therefore proposed in this section to perform 3D FE analyses to investigate the consequences.

Fig. 14: Overview of the 3D FE model. Only half of each slit tape is meshed.

Fig. 14 shows an isomeric overview of the proposed 3D FE mesh capturing a single tape/tape gap. This choice was made to reduce the computation times. This is suitable anyway for predicting what happens to most of the tapes except for the two peripheral ones, namely tapes 1 and 8 in Fig. 8. It is also important to note that the proposed 3D approach

assumes no deviation of the tapes' vertical planes of symmetry during the whole process.

Overall, the 3D mesh is similar to the 2D one as viewed from the lateral side parallel to the x-y-plane. 8-noded fully integrated hexahedral elements of type C3D8 were used to mesh both the roller and the tapes. 4-noded rigid elements of type R3D4 were used to mesh the bearing surface tie-constrained to the inner surface of the deformable part of the roller. All the boundary conditions were similar to those used in the 2D model in Fig. 9. However, the nodes on the two lateral faces parallel to the x-y plane were constrained in the z-direction. This made the roller behave under plane strain conditions and enabled the vertical planes of symmetry of the 2 slit tapes to be properly constrained. As for the 2D simulations, the 3D ones were limited to the first 100 mm of the tapes to reduce the computation times. The calculations were also broken down into the two distinct steps as previously discussed in section 3.1.

Fig. 15: Predicted tape thickness distributions from the 3D model at the tapes' vertical planes of symmetry ($t_t = 0.283$ mm and $w_g = 0.2$ mm). Each curve is for a given compaction load and a constant layup temperature at 30°C .

Fig. 16: Predicted tape/tape gap width distributions at 30°C from the 3D FE model as a function of the compaction load ($t_t = 0.283$ mm and $w_g = 0.2$ mm).

Fig. 15 shows how the surfaces of the tapes are deformed at their vertical symmetry planes when the prepreg is at 30°C. Compared to the 2D cases, the initial gap width, w_g , was here reduced down to 0.2 mm to make sure that the tapes interact with each other at some layup conditions.

Fig. 16 shows the simulated tape/tape gap width distributions at 30°C for various compaction loads ranging from 100 to 600 N. It can be noticed that lateral contact occurs from the elastic bumps where the roller is still compacting the prepreg. Once this occurs at 500 N onwards, no further thickness and gap reductions is observed in the results.

Fig. 17: Predicted tape thickness distributions from the 3D model at the tapes' vertical planes of symmetry ($t_t = 0.283$ mm and $w_g = 0.2$ mm). Each curve is for a given compaction load and a constant layup temperature at 40°C.

Fig. 18: Predicted tape/tape gap width distributions at 40°C from the 3D FE model as a function of the compaction load ($t_t = 0.283$ mm and $w_g = 0.2$ mm).

On the other hand, when the layup temperature is higher, i.e. at 40°C, the material becomes more compliant and lateral contact between the tapes occurs from a much lower compaction load i.e. 200 N, see Figs. 17 and 18. As for the 30°C layup case, no benefit is obtained by further increasing the load.

Optimal layup conditions can therefore be predicted from the model in terms of load and prepreg temperature. It is important to note that the results at 20°C did not lead to any tape/tape lateral contact, and therefore no curve has been reported in this paper.

Fig. 19: Final slit tape thickness as functions of the compaction load for various layup temperatures (initial gap width $w_g = 0.2$ mm). Dashed and continuous lines are from 2D and 3D results respectively.

Fig. 20: Tape/tape gap width as functions of the compaction load for various layup temperatures (initial gap width $w_g = 0.2$ mm). Dashed and continuous lines are from 2D and 3D results respectively.

Figs. 19 and 20 respectively show the graphs plotting the final tape thickness and tape/tape gap width against the compaction load for various layup temperatures. Dashed lines and continuous lines were plotted from the 2D and 3D FE results respectively. 3D results were obtained with and without lateral tape/tape contact to rigorously compare the predictions with the 2D ones.

Globally, similar predictions were obtained from both the 2D and 3D FE analyses when tape/tape lateral contact was ignored. Higher thickness and

gap width values were however obtained in 3D because of the triaxiality in the strain tensor which captures inter alia lateral effects. These effects are exacerbated with the prepreg temperature because it becomes more compliant. As already discussed on the 2D results, most of the deformation is accumulated through the thickness while, in 3D, the latter is slit into through-thickness and lateral components. This means that 2D analyses are convenient for predicting the final shape of the slit tapes only when the prepreg is stiff enough to limit the magnitude of plastic deformations.

When tape/tape contact is activated in the FE model, the graphs in Figs. 19 and 20 show that the 3D results at 30 and 40°C deviate from those produced when neglecting lateral effects after given loads. This occurs from $F_c = 500$ N at 30°C and from $F_c = 200$ N at 40°C. As demonstrated previously in Figs. 16 and 18, this is caused by the interaction between the elastic bumps at the actual position of the roller. No deflection is observed at 20°C because tape/tape lateral contact was non-existent.

Interestingly, both the red (40°C) 3D curves in Figs. 19 and 20 converge towards higher values than that for the blue (30°C) 3D ones when F_c increases. This seems to be due to the higher lateral contact forces generated at 40°C than at 30°C. No deep investigation into the causes was however conducted because of the relative small difference between the results (0.2 % in Fig. 19 and 12 % in Fig. 20) which are partially caused by the precision in the experimental results.

Fig. 21: Final slit tape thickness as functions of the compaction load for various layup temperatures. All the lines are from 3D results including an initial gap width $w_g = 0.1$ mm.

Fig. 22: Tape/tape gap width as functions of the compaction load for various layup temperatures. All the lines are from 3D results including an initial gap width $w_g = 0.1$ mm.

Subsequently, it was chosen to investigate the influence of the initial tape/tape gap width, w_g , on the final slit tape cross section. It was therefore proposed to further reduce w_g down to 0.1 mm to verify whether the gap could completely be closed. Such a value is at the lower limit of accuracy of recent AFP machines [9].

Unlike the results reported in Figs. 19 and 20, the new results in Figs. 21 and 22 do not include any 2D result (dashed lines) to lighten the amount of information plotted. However, and as shown previously, divergence is observed between the 3D results including tape/tape interactions and those neglecting them but at lower F_c values. The higher the layup temperature is, the lower the compaction load needs to be to start observing deviation: 400 N at 20°C, 200 N at 30°C, and 100 N at 40°C. An average 0.281 mm final prepreg thickness is obtained from the 3 chosen temperatures in Fig. 21. This is of the same order of magnitude to the thickness value predicted in Fig. 19 by bearing in mind that the mean tape roughness amplitude, R_z , is 0.046 mm for the prepreg used [25]. These results confirm that the elastic bumps contacting each other do prevent any non-zero initial gap from closing. In other words, they act as a barrier beyond which plastic flow is not allowed to propagate.

Regarding the final tape/tape gap width predictions in Fig. 22, all the curves converge towards the same 0.054 mm average gap width value for the 3 layup temperatures. This is about twice lower than the gap width values reported in Fig. 20. This means that reducing the initial gap width value, w_g , makes it possible to reduce the final gap width but not

completely regardless of the prepreg temperature. However, the higher the layup temperature, the lower the required load for obtaining the same results observed at high compaction loads.

5. Conclusions

This paper was concerned with the prediction of the final shape of 8 slit tapes laid down simultaneously onto a rigid flat panel during AFP. Isothermal conditions were assumed throughout. Both the roller and the uncured prepreg were characterised experimentally prior to simulating. Effective isotropic elastic properties were used to model the roller. The uncured prepreg was modelled as an elasto-plastic material following the conclusions made by Lukaszewicz and Potter [19].

2D and 3D FE analyses were undertaken then compared. Qualitatively, 2D FE models predicted similar results to the 3D model. They are appropriate for predicting the final thickness of single slit tape as well as final tape/tape gap width only when the prepreg is stiff enough which may be the case at room temperature. This is also valid as long as no lateral tape/tape interaction occurs, otherwise 3D models are required.

By using the latter, it was found that they can help optimise AFP process parameters. The simulation results showed that, for a given layup temperature, no benefit is obtained by further increasing the compaction load once lateral tape/tape contact occurs from the lateral elastic “bumps” at the actual position of the roller. Indeed, these ‘bumps’ prevent plastic flow from spreading laterally and therefore prevent the gaps from closing. This may therefore provide channels that would help evacuate entrapped air during debulk operations. Work is underway at the NCC to experimentally verify the simulation results, improve the roller material model, and to add viscous effects into the prepreg material model.

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